

Report:

A2.3.4

Deliverable D4: "Report on the use of a calibrated microfluidic multi-parameter chip for the in-line measurement of pressure, viscosity and temperature."

This report was written as part of activity 2.3.4 from the EMPIR Metrology for Drug Delivery (MeDD II) project. The three-year European project commenced on 1st June 2019 and focused on providing traceable measurements of volume, flow and pressure of existing drug delivery devices and mixing behavior and occlusion phenomena in multi-infusion systems. For more details about this project, please visit www.drugmetrology.com

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The EMPIR initiative is co-funded by the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme and the EMPIR Participating States

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Introduction to the EMPIR Metrology for Drug Delivery project

The overall aim of this project is to improve dosing accuracy and to enable the traceable measurement of volume, flow and pressure in existing drug delivery devices and in-line sensors operating at very low flow rates. This will be achieved through the development of new calibration methods and by expanding the existing metrological infrastructure. This project will also investigate fast changing flow rates, which are step changes between two flow rates within a second, the physical properties of mixtures of liquids and occlusion phenomena in multi-infusion systems in order to prevent inaccurate measurement results and thus to improve patient safety.

The specific objectives of the project are:

1. To develop new traceable techniques for generating and measuring the response or delay time of drug delivery devices regarding changes in flow rate, from 5 nL/min to 100 nL/min, using Newtonian liquids (WP1). For steady flow rates an uncertainty of 1 % ($k=2$) or better is expected, whereas for fast changing flow rates an uncertainty of 2 % ($k=2$) or better is expected. The techniques developed will be used to characterise and validate the different response times of at least 3 different types of drug delivery devices (including infusion analysers) (WP3 and WP4) and one type of flow sensor, to accurately measure the administered flow and volume with the required uncertainties.
2. To upgrade the existing flow facilities and knowledge of the partner NMIs in order to enable the traceable in-line measurement of the dynamic viscosity of Newtonian liquids, as a function of the flow rate and pressure difference, with a target uncertainty value of 2 % ($k=2$). The measurement uncertainty will be validated using Newtonian liquids with traceable dynamic viscosity calibration. Additionally, tests with non-Newtonian liquids will be performed in order to prove the concept. To calibrate transfer standards for the in-line measurement of dynamic viscosity and other physical properties of liquids, in order to use these transfer standards for flow measurement and to determine the mixing behaviour of different liquids.
3. To develop and validate novel calibration procedures for existing medical flow devices (e.g. infusion pumps, pain controllers and infusion pump analysers) with traceability to a primary standard and with a target uncertainty value of 2 % ($k=2$) for a range of 5 nL/min up to 600 ml/min and also to develop a proof-of-concept on-chip microfluidic pump used as a transfer standard in drug discovery and organ-on-a-chip applications for flow rates lower than 100 nL/min.
4. To design and develop a multi-infusion system containing check valves, with several options for testing how liquids, with different viscosities mix and flow and how this affects drug concentration. The flow rates and pressures will be traceably calibrated in all infusion lines, as well as at the outlet of the syringe pump, to be able to analyse the effects of pressure-equalising devices and to detect occlusion phenomena and bad mixing configurations.
5. To facilitate the take up of the technology and measurement infrastructure developed in the project by the measurement supply chain (i.e. accredited laboratories, instrumentation manufacturers, etc.), standards developing organisations (ISO/TC 30, ISO/TC 48, ISO/TC/SC 62D, ISO/TC 69, ISO/TC 76, ISO/TC 84, ISO/TC 150, ISO/TC 210) and end-users (i.e. hospitals and health centres).

Activity 2.3.4 – report on the use of a calibrated microfluidic multi-parameter chip for the in-line measurement of pressure, viscosity and temperature

Overall Objective: Using input from A2.3.1-A2.3.3, IPQ, METAS, KRISS, NEL, RISE and BHT will write a report on the use of a calibrated microfluidic multi-parameter chip for the in-line measurement of pressure, viscosity and temperature.

Once agreed by the consortium, the coordinator will then submit the report to EURAMET as **D4**: *‘Report on the use of a calibrated microfluidic multi-parameter chip for the in-line measurement of pressure, viscosity and temperature’*

The following Institutes have contributed to this Deliverable:

no	Participant Type	Short Name	Organisation legal full name	Country
1	Internal Funded Partner	IPQ	Instituto Português da Qualidade, I.P.	Portugal
5	Internal Funded Partner	METAS	Eidgenössisches Institut für Metrologie METAS	Switzerland
6	Internal Funded Partner	NEL	TUV SUD Limited	United Kingdom
8	Internal Funded Partner	RISE	RISE Research Institutes of Sweden AB	Sweden
15	Unfunded Partner	BHT	Bronkhorst High-Tech BV	Netherlands
16	Unfunded Partner	KRISS	Korea Research Institute of Standards and Science	Republic of Korea

The progress within this report covers the Period from 1st June 2019 to the end of August 2022.

1 Introduction

In-line measurements of liquid properties are important for production processes or applications where different liquids are mixed. In healthcare applications, such as multi-infusion systems, different drugs are mixed to be administered to the patient via a central catheter. Investigating the mixing behaviour requires knowledge of the liquid properties prior and after various mixing points. Therefore, sensors for the in-line measurement of pressure, viscosity and temperature are indispensable for the determination of the mixing behaviour or clogging phenomena in several infusion lines. The calibration of sensors containing a microfluidic chip for the in-line measurement of liquid properties and issues in using these sensors are described and discussed in this report.

2 Sensor for in-line measurement of density, dynamic viscosity, pressure and temperature of liquids

Two sensors for in-line measurements of physical properties of liquids have been investigated.

One sensor is the VLO-M1 sensor from TrueDyne Sensors AG [1], which measures the temperature, density, kinematic viscosity and dynamic viscosity of the liquid.

The second sensor is the multi-parameter chip sensor from Bronkhorst High-Tech B.V. [2-4], which measures mass flow, chip inlet and the outlet pressure, density, dynamic viscosity and temperature.

These two sensors are described in the next sections and measurement results are presented. Most of the measurements were performed with the eight liquids A – H with traceable density and dynamic viscosity described and characterised in report A2.1.2.

2.1 The microfluidic multi-parameter chip from Bronkhorst High-Tech BV

The multi-parameter microchip from Bronkhorst High-Tech B.V. is a technology demonstrator and not commercially available.

2.1.1 Description of the Multi-parameter Measurement System (MMS)

The MMS from Bronkhorst High-Tech B.V. used for the measurement of density and dynamic viscosity in this project contains the multi-parameter chip consisting of the micro-Coriolis flow sensor and two pressure sensors, as shown in Figure 1 [2]. Additionally, to the micro-Coriolis flow sensor, a thermal sensor can be implemented on the chip, which enables the measurement of heat capacity, thermal conductivity, density and kinematic and dynamic viscosity of the liquid [3]. Further developments will allow the measurement of the relative dielectric constant of the liquid by measuring the capacitance between an electrode on the top of the channel and the grounded substrate [4].

Figure 1: Multi-parameter chip of Bronkhorst High Tech B.V. containing the micro Coriolis flow sensor and two pressure sensors used for the measurements of the density and the dynamic viscosity of the liquids.

The multi-parameter chip available for the measurements during the project was the version limited to the measurement of the dynamic viscosity, density and temperature. The measurement system containing the multi-parameter chip was tested for functionality at Bronkhorst High-Tech B.V. and then sent to METAS. At METAS, the multi-parameter measurement system was installed in the METAS pipe viscometer facility, as can be seen in Figure 2. Unfortunately, the initial measurements showed unstable results for the dynamic viscosity. It might be that the multi-parameter chip was slightly damaged during transportation. Fortunately, the results for density proved to be stable. Therefore, only the density measurements for liquids A, B, E and F are presented in this report.

Figure 2: The Multiparameter Measurement System from Bronkhorst High-Tech B.V. (a light grey box containing the multi-parameter chip and its electronics) installed at the METAS pipe viscometer facility.

2.1.2 Density measurements with the liquids A, B, E and F

As the reference density values of the eight liquids A – H are known for the temperature range between 20 °C and 30 °C (Report A2.1.2), the actual temperature measured by the multi-parameter chip was used to calculate the reference density at the actual measurement temperature, which was at 32.9 °C. The results are listed in Table 1.

Table 1. Reference value of the density extrapolated to the temperature of 32.9 °C according to the temperature dependence reported in Report A2.1.2 (measured by the laboratory IPQ) and the results of the Multiparameter Measurement System (MMS). The results presented are the values including the expanded measurement uncertainty $U(k=2)$. The deviation of the MMS with respect to the reference value and its measurement uncertainty is also represented in this table.

	Liquid A	Liquid B	Liquid E	Liquid F
Reference value (kg/m ³)	1001.06 ± 0.05	1034.67 ± 0.05	1016.94 ± 0.05	1018.57 ± 0.05
MMS (kg/m ³)	996.9 ± 5.0	1025.8 ± 5.0	1012.2 ± 5.0	1012.9 ± 5.0
MMS Deviation (%)	-0.42 ± 0.50	-0.85 ± 0.50	-0.46 ± 0.50	-0.55 ± 0.50

The deviations of the density measurements from the calculated reference values are less than 1 %, which corresponds to the estimated measurement uncertainty of the actual setup of the technology demonstrator. Further developments of the technology demonstrator aim at an uncertainty of 0.5 % for the density measurement. Therefore, the uncertainty of 0.5 % is given in Table 1.

2.1.3 Density and viscosity measurements with water, IPA, acetone and ethanol

The measurement setup for the results shown in this paper consist of a liquid vessel positioned inside a pressure vessel that generates a flow by means of overpressure (Figure 3). The liquid flows through a degasser and into the multi-parameter chip, which is located in an incubator with all the electronics to ensure stable temperature conditions. The liquid is then directed to a mass flow controller that adjusts the flow rate and is discharged into a waste container. The measurements were performed at each set point for 3 minutes with a reading interval of 2 s after a stabilization time, where all the sensors had to be stable within 0.1 % for at least 2 minutes. The housing temperature was set to 19 °C, 24 °C and 29 °C and the inlet pressure was adjusted from 4 bar to 6 bar in steps of 0.5 bar. The flow rates were set from 0 g/h to 5 g/h in steps of 0.5 g/h.

Figure 3: Measurement setup with the multi-parameter chip at Bronkhorst High Tech B.V.

The data shown in Figure 4 and Figure 5 are averaged values for inlet pressures from 4 bar to 6 bar and flow rates from 3 g/h to 5 g/h, with very little dependence on flow rate and negligible dependence on pressure. All density measurements results shown in Figure 4 and Table 2 are within ±0.2 % of the theoretical values [5]. At flow rates lower than 3 g/h, the density measurements of IPA, acetone and ethanol are within ± 0.7 %, which is still an acceptable accuracy. The results of the dynamic viscosity

measurements, shown in Figure 5 and Table 3, are within $\pm 1.6\%$. Looking at the data for flow rates lower than 3 g/h, the deviations of the dynamic viscosity are between -2 % and +4 % for water, between -2 % and +2 % for IPA, between -2 % and +2 % for ethanol and between -6 % and +15 % for acetone. These deviations are flow rate and temperature dependent and only slightly pressure dependent. The dynamic viscosity results for water, IPA and ethanol are within $\pm 4\%$ for all flow rates. Further investigations are needed to explain the results for acetone.

Figure 4: Deviations of the density of water (black square), IPA (red circle), Acetone (green triangle), Ethanol (blue diamond) measured by the multi-parameter chip with respect to the theoretical values. The errors bars represent three times the standard deviation of each measurement value of each set point.

Table 2. Results of density measurements with the multi-parameter chip as a function of the housing temperature (incubator). The uncertainties given represent three times the standard deviation of the measurement value of each set point. The absolute values in the unit kg/m^3 and the deviation with respect to the theoretical values in % are presented.

	Housing temperature	Water	IPA	Acetone	Ethanol
Density (kg/m^3)	19 °C	997.82 ± 0.03	790.57 ± 0.12	794.59 ± 0.10	803.96 ± 0.12
Deviation (%)		-0.008 ± 0.004	-0.132 ± 0.018	0.034 ± 0.014	0.011 ± 0.016
Density (kg/m^3)	24 °C	996.65 ± 0.05	784.84 ± 0.12	787.99 ± 0.11	798.24 ± 0.12
Deviation (%)		-0.001 ± 0.006	-0.174 ± 0.021	0.006 ± 0.015	-0.042 ± 0.016
Density (kg/m^3)	29 °C	995.07 ± 0.07	780.48 ± 0.10	781.97 ± 0.11	793.08 ± 0.11
Deviation (%)		-0.013 ± 0.008	-0.047 ± 0.014	0.042 ± 0.015	-0.027 ± 0.015

Figure 5: Deviations of the dynamic viscosity of water (black square), IPA (red circle), Acetone (green triangle), Ethanol (blue diamond) measured by the multi-parameter chip with respect to the theoretical values. The errors bars represent three times the standard deviation of each measurement value of each set point and not the measurement uncertainty.

Table 3. Results of dynamic viscosity measurements with the multi-parameter chip as a function of the housing temperature (incubator). The uncertainties given represent three times the standard deviation of the measurement value of each set point. The absolute values in the unit mPa·s and the deviation with respect to the theoretical values in % are presented.

	Housing temperature	Water	IPA	Acetone	Ethanol
Dynamic viscosity (mPa·s)	19 °C	0.960 ± 0.007	2.157 ± 0.016	0.317 ± 0.003	1.102 ± 0.004
Deviation (%)		-0.6 ± 1.1	-0.44 ± 0.99	1.58 ± 0.91	0.52 ± 0.39
Dynamic viscosity (mPa·s)	24 °C	0.861 ± 0.003	1.857 ± 0.011	0.299 ± 0.007	1.000 ± 0.004
Deviation (%)		-0.19 ± 0.40	-0.54 ± 0.69	0.5 ± 2.8	0.22 ± 0.40
Dynamic viscosity (mPa·s)	29 °C	0.779 ± 0.003	1.607 ± 0.011	0.280 ± 0.009	0.915 ± 0.005
Deviation (%)		0.29 ± 0.43	-0.87 ± 0.71	-1.3 ± 3.4	0.38 ± 0.54

2.2 The VLO-M1 including the Omega chip from TrueDyne Sensors AG

The VLO-M1 sensor from TrueDyne Sensors AG is commercially available.

2.2.1 Description of the Omega chip integrated in the VLO-M1

The VLO-M1 sensor from TrueDyne Sensors AG measures the temperature, density, kinematic and dynamic viscosity of a liquid flowing through the sensor. The measuring principle is based on the Coriolis measurement principle [1,6].

Figure 6: VLO-M1 sensor from TrueDyne Sensors AG [1].

The sensor is constructed with a bypass arrangement as shown in Figure 7, where the microelectromechanical system (MEMS) with the omega-shaped microchannel (Omega chip) is connected to the bypass [1].

Figure 7: Illustration of the tubing in the VLO-M2 and the connected Omega Chip [1].

The Omega chip consists of a silicon tube that is electrostatically vibrated in a vacuum [6] and allows the measurement of the density, kinematic and dynamic viscosity as well as the temperature of the liquid in the tube. The bottom and top of the Omega chip are presented in Figure 8.

Figure 8: The Omega Chip [6]. Left: bottom view with fluid connection holes. Right: top view with electrical connections and tweezers to illustrate the size.

2.2.2 Density and viscosity measurements with the eight liquids A - H

Measurements were performed with the VLO-M1 sensor and the eight liquids A – H (details in report A2.1.2), and the results are in excellent agreement with the reference values of density (Table 4) and dynamic viscosity (Table 5) of the eight liquids (details in report A2.1.4).

Table 4. Reference value of the density measured by the laboratory IPQ (Report 2.1.4) and the results of the VLO-M1 sensor at a temperature of 22 °C. The results presented are the values \pm the expanded measurement uncertainty $U(k=2)$. The deviation of the VLO-M1 with respect to the reference value and its measurement uncertainty is also represented in this table.

	Liquid A	Liquid B	Liquid C	Liquid D	Liquid E	Liquid F	Liquid G	Liquid H
Reference value (kg/m ³)	1004.172 \pm 0.033	1038.171 \pm 0.033	1079.829 \pm 0.033	1010.362 \pm 0.033	1020.217 \pm 0.033	1021.882 \pm 0.033	1131.303 \pm 0.033	1150.192 \pm 0.033
VLO-M1 (kg/m ³)	1004.29 \pm 0.20	1038.30 \pm 0.20	1079.76 \pm 0.20	1010.47 \pm 0.20	1020.32 \pm 0.20	1021.97 \pm 0.20	1131.42 \pm 0.20	1150.41 \pm 0.20
VLO-M1 Deviation (%)	0.011 \pm 0.020	0.012 \pm 0.020	-0.006 \pm 0.019	0.010 \pm 0.020	0.010 \pm 0.020	0.009 \pm 0.020	0.011 \pm 0.018	0.019 \pm 0.018

Table 5. The reference values (Report A2.1.4) and the results of the VLO-M1 sensor for the measurement of the dynamic viscosity of the eight liquids at a temperature of 22 °C. The deviation of the VLO-M1 with respect to the reference value and its measurement uncertainty is also represented in this table.

	Liquid A	Liquid B	Liquid C	Liquid D	Liquid E	Liquid F	Liquid G	Liquid H
Reference value (mPa·s)	0.972 \pm 0.005	1.274 \pm 0.007	1.809 \pm 0.009	1.045 \pm 0.006	1.116 \pm 0.006	1.115 \pm 0.007	6.310 \pm 0.038	9.453 \pm 0.051
VLO-M1 (mPa·s)	0.945 \pm 0.047	1.239 \pm 0.062	1.740 \pm 0.087	1.013 \pm 0.050	1.077 \pm 0.054	1.080 \pm 0.054	6.15 \pm 0.31	9.44 \pm 0.47
VLO-M1 Deviation (%)	-2.8 \pm 5.0	-2.8 \pm 5.0	-3.8 \pm 5.0	-3.0 \pm 5.0	-3.5 \pm 5.0	-3.1 \pm 5.0	-2.5 \pm 5.0	-0.2 \pm 5.0

3 Important notes for the calibration

3.1 Temperature measurement

At this point it is important to mention that the temperature measurement of the sensors is performed on the internal tube, where the liquid is flowing through and the measurements of density and dynamic viscosity are performed. As the chip is inside the housing with the electronics, a heating effect by the electronics can be observed. This means that the temperature of the liquid before and after the sensor can deviate from the temperature measured in the sensor. These temperature differences must be characterized. The best solution is to measure the temperature of the liquid with an appropriate sensor in the tubing which is connected to the sensor. The knowledge of the temperature difference enables the calculation of the density and the dynamic viscosity at an arbitrary position in the tubing where the temperature is measured. Obviously, for such temperature corrections of the density and the dynamic viscosity, the temperature dependence of the density and the dynamic viscosity must be known.

The heating effect by the electronics has been observed with the VLO-M1 sensor, where the temperature of the liquid in the tubing was 22.25 °C, whereas the temperature in the sensor was varying between 22.40 °C and 22.60 °C, depending on the flow rate.

The multi-parameter chip showed an even worse heating effect, where the temperature measured in the sensor was above 32 °C, whereas the temperature in the tubing upstream of the sensor was 22.20 °C.

3.2 Pressure measurement

The microfluidic chip also offers the possibility to measure the pressure at the position of the sensor in the tubing. It is important to be aware of the fact that the sensor itself generates a pressure drop. The knowledge of this pressure drop as a function of the flow rate is important and the ratio is called the flow resistance of the sensor. The flow resistance can be measured by mounting calibrated pressure sensors upstream and downstream of the sensor and measuring the pressure drop of the sensor by subtracting the pressure drop of the connectors at different flow rates.

The pressure sensors on the chip can be calibrated with static pressure measurements where no pressure drop occurs through the sensor as no flow is present. It is important to wait for stabilization of the pressure in the tubing and the sensor to avoid systematic errors considering these small dimensions of the tubing.

3.3 Temperature dependence of density and dynamic viscosity of reference liquids

The temperature dependence of the density and dynamic viscosity of reference liquids must be known in order to calibrate the sensor for density and dynamic viscosity measurement. The sensor measures the temperature of the internal tube where the density and the dynamic viscosity are determined. The knowledge of temperature dependence of the density and the dynamic viscosity allows the interpolation of the reference values to the temperature measured by the sensor. The comparison of the measurement results at this temperature with the reference values at the same temperature makes it possible to determine the deviation of the values obtained by the sensor from the reference values.

4 Traceability of the dynamic viscosity measurements

Capillary glass viscometers are widely used and their method is well-established worldwide for traceable measurement of the kinematic viscosity to SI units. However, this technique does not allow the in-line measurement of the dynamic viscosity in flow applications, which is important for the process-oriented information on the dynamic viscosity of the liquid. The micro pipe viscometers enable the characterisation of liquids under flow conditions and the direct calibration of devices measuring dynamic viscosity under flow conditions or the investigation of the influence of dynamic viscosity on the performance of flow devices with traceability to SI units (details in report A2.1.5).

5 Pressure drop of the sensor to be taken into consideration

In addition to the aspects discussed in chapter 3, the pressure drop of the sensor must be taken into account so that the sensor can be used to measure liquid properties without the flow behaviour being disturbed by the additional pressure drop in the tubing for any application or in infusion lines in multi-infusion systems.

5.1 Pressure drop of MMS

The pressure drop of the MMS was determined by measurements with water (dynamic viscosity about 1 mPa·s) and the pressure drop normalised by the flow rate is 0.42 bar/(mL/h). The pressure drop is too high for the use in multi-infusion systems as it affects the behaviour of any multi-infusion system. The reason for the high-pressure drop is the small inner diameter of the multi-parameter chip of approx. 50 µm. New multi-parameter chips with larger inner diameters up to 1 mm are in preparation.

5.2 Pressure drop of the VLO-M1

The pressure drop of the VLO-M1 was determined by measurements with water (dynamic viscosity about 1 mPa·s) and the pressure drop normalised by the flow rate is $2 \cdot 10^{-5}$ bar/(mL/h). The pressure drop is negligible, but the suitability of the sensor at the flow rates for the multi-infusion system needs to be clarified. The sensor has a bypass where a pressure drop is created at the inlet to force the liquid through the bypass.

6 Conclusion

The microfluidic chips of the commercially available sensor VLO-M1 sensor from TrueDyne Sensors AG and the technology demonstrator MMS from Bronkhorst High-Tech BV measure the viscosity, density and temperature of the liquid.

The measurement results of the commercially available VLO-M1 sensor for density and dynamic viscosity are well within the specifications of the manufacturer. The measured flow resistance of the sensor is relatively low and it would even be possible to implement this sensor in a multi-infusion system for the investigation of the mixing behaviour of different drugs in R&D activities.

The technology demonstrator has been used to measure the density of several liquids, and the target accuracy has almost been achieved. Additional measurement results for density and dynamic viscosity have demonstrated the functionality of the multi-parameter chip in the MMS. However, the actual pressure drop of the sensor is relatively high, which could affect the mixing behaviour in a multi-infusion system. The reason for the high-pressure drop is the small inner diameter of the multi-parameter chip of approx. 50 µm. Multi-parameter chips with larger inner diameters up to 1 mm are in preparation to decrease the flow resistance of the chip.

The microfluidic chips can be calibrated for the measurement of pressure, density, dynamic viscosity and temperature. The report highlights several temperature and pressure effects that must be considered when calibrating the microfluidic chip

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